

FIRE AS A FACTOR OF TECHNOGENIC DISASTER

Makhmatkulov Nurilla Imomovich

Senior Lecturer

Karshi Engineering and Economic Institute

Department of Labor Protection and Technical Safety

Abstract: This article provides general concepts about fire safety and classifies materials according to their fire resistance, as well as presents the responsibilities and powers of subjects to implement measures to ensure fire safety.

Key words and phrases: Fire, fire safety, preventive measures, fire resistance, civil protection, emergency situations, life safety, material costs.

Fires cause enormous material damage and in some cases are accompanied by loss of life. Therefore, fire protection is the most important responsibility of every member of society and is carried out on a national scale.

Today, increasing the effectiveness of protecting citizens and the country's economy from disasters is receiving increased attention, both from the state and society as a whole. Achieving this goal is ensured by the formation of a culture of safe life in society, the creation and implementation of innovations in the prevention and response to emergency situations.

A timely and balanced decision in the current situation is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Fire Safety". which determines the main directions for ensuring public safety, reducing deaths and injuries in emergency situations and at work, and increases the responsibility of managers at various levels. A lot of efforts are aimed at creating a culture of life safety among the population and, moreover, changing a person's worldview on safety issues. Employees of the

Ministry of Emergency Situations in educational institutions constantly train pupils and students in emergency situations.

Also, to achieve the goal, outdoor billboards with a social theme are produced and installed, aimed at preventing the death of people in fires due to careless handling of fire. In addition to fire prevention propaganda and training of the population, practical preventive measures are also carried out in a timely manner to bring households of large families, single elderly and disabled people, citizens living alone over working age in a fire-safe state.

However, in general, the set of measures being carried out in the Republic does not allow stabilizing the situation with fires and the death of people in them. In just 8 months of 2023, 667 emergencies occurred, of which 554 were fires. About 90% of fires occurred in the residential sector. The cause of fires is mainly careless handling of fire and accounts for 64%, faulty electrical wiring 16%, faulty stove heating 13%, other causes 7%.

A radical improvement in the situation with the deaths of people in fires is possible only with the active and direct participation of all government bodies, local executive and administrative bodies, providing targeted and targeted funding for fire-fighting activities, strengthening the material and technical base of emergency departments and units.

What is a fire?

A fire is a combustion outside a special source that is not controlled and can lead to mass casualties and deaths, as well as environmental, material and other damage.

Fire protection of any facility is aimed at finding the most effective, economically feasible and technically sound methods and means of preventing fires and extinguishing them with minimal damage with the most rational use of forces and technical means of extinguishing.

Fire safety is a state of a national economic facility in which the possibility

of a fire is excluded, and if it occurs, the necessary measures are taken to eliminate the negative impact of fire hazards on people, structures and material assets [1].

These measures can be ensured by fire prevention and active fire protection measures. Fire prevention includes a set of measures aimed at preventing a fire or reducing its consequences. Active fire protection - measures aimed at ensuring the fight against fires or explosive situations.

A fire is accompanied by combustion, gas and heat exchange. Fires can be open, closed, massive, continuous and heavy. Depending on the type of burning materials and substances, fires are divided into 5 main classes:

A - combustion of solids (wood, paper);

B - combustion of flammable combustible liquids (fuel oil, alcohol, gasoline);

C - combustion of gases (hydrogen, acetylene, hydrocarbons);

D - combustion of metals (Na, K, Al, Mg);

E - electrical installations under voltage.

The main damaging factors of a fire can be open fire, sparks, thermal radiation, smoke, low oxygen concentration, toxic combustion products (hydrocyanic acid, carbon monoxide, phosgene, acrylonitrile), falling objects and structures [2].

Each fire has its own characteristic signs. The black color of the smoke indicates the presence of soot in the fire, which is typical for the combustion of petroleum products, rubber, and coal. Light smoke indicates the presence of magnesium oxides and a significant amount of water vapor.

Depending on the volume of oxygen, the flame can be non-luminous (up to 50%) and luminous (over 50%). In the presence of carbon in burning substances, the flame is accompanied by the release of soot. By the specific smell, color, taste, and effects on the mucous membranes of the eyes, nose, and respiratory tract,

rescuers can determine the presence of hazardous substances in the air (smoke). The characteristic features of such substances are presented in table. 1.

The main methods of stopping combustion used when extinguishing fires are:

-cooling the combustion zone with water, wetting solutions, carbon dioxide and other fire extinguishing agents, which take away part of the heat used to continue combustion;

- dilution of substances reacting during the combustion process with water vapor, carbon dioxide, nitrogen and other gases that do not support combustion.

Table- 1

Ammonia	Pungent odor, irritates the respiratory tract, causes watery eyes and pain in the eyes, coughing
Hydrogen chloride	Pungent odor, strongly irritates the respiratory tract, causes hoarseness, a feeling of suffocation
Hydrogen cyanide	Smell of bitter almonds, scratchy sensation in the throat, burning bitter taste in the mouth
Sulfur gas	Pungent odor, very small concentrations irritate the mucous membranes of the eyes and respiratory tract, higher concentrations lead to hoarseness
Formaldehyde	Looks like dense white smoke, irritates the mucous membranes of the eyes, nose, and respiratory tract
Chlorine	Greenish-yellow gas with a pungent odor that irritates the respiratory tract

Depending on the types of fires, it is necessary to use different extinguishing methods. The most common means of extinguishing a fire is water. When it hits burning material, it cools it; steam is formed, which prevents the flow of oxygen to the combustion site. But it cannot be used when extinguishing

flammable substances with a density lower than the density of water, as well as not de-energized wires and electrical installations.

To extinguish other categories of fires, other fire extinguishing agents are used. These include fire extinguishing foams (chemical and air-mechanical), inert gases, carbon dioxide and solid fire extinguishing agents [3].

In any case, preventing a fire is cheaper than extinguishing it. Therefore, at any facility it is necessary to carry out a set of measures. These include fire prevention and fire safety.

Fire prevention is a set of organizational and technical measures to prevent, localize and eliminate fires, as well as to ensure the safe evacuation of people and property in the event of fires.

Fire safety is a state of an industrial facility in which the possibility of a fire is excluded, and if it occurs, the impact of hazardous factors on people is prevented and material assets are protected.

Fire safety of industrial enterprises consists of a fire prevention system, a fire protection system and organizational and technical measures.

For each enterprise, in accordance with the Order of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of fire safety standards “Training in fire safety measures for employees of organizations””, general facility and workshop instructions on fire safety measures are developed [4].

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The instructions on fire safety measures also establish the procedure for using fire extinguishing agents and calling fire assistance in the event of a fire at

the enterprise. The procedure for storing flammable liquids and flammable liquids, collecting, storing and disposing of cleaning materials and industrial combustible waste, maintaining and storing workwear, as well as the responsibilities and actions of workers and employees in case of a fire are determined [5].

Thus, it is obvious that management in the field of fire safety in the Republic falls not only within the competence of emergency authorities and departments, but also within the competence of local and self-government bodies, as well as the entire population, in connection with which the latter must take direct and effective participation in resolving emerging issues and not abstracting themselves from their solution.

Taking into account the above, in order to increase the level of life safety of the population, within the framework of the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Fire Safety”, it is necessary to apply additional measures for prompt response, development and implementation of timely targeted solutions aimed at the life safety of citizens, namely:

- within the framework of the National Security Concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan, pay special attention to combining the efforts of prevention subjects to eliminate the causes and conditions conducive to the commission of offenses;

- quarterly review the results of the ongoing work to ensure fire safety with district chairmen, assessing the role of each prevention subject in the work being carried out;

- ensure the implementation of plans for the priority repair of stoves, electrical wiring, installation of autonomous fire detectors, if possible with signal output to alarm sound devices or to neighboring houses (apartments), in households of the above category of citizens who are most in need of this work;

- taking into account the results of inspections of the housing stock, send letters to children of this category of citizens with information about the need to

immediately take measures to repair (replace) stoves and (or) electrical wiring that are in a fire-hazardous condition, the need to install API in residential premises;

- personally assign large families to employees of education departments of district executive committees, heads of educational institutions to organize preventive, explanatory work, monitor the provision of safe living conditions for children with monthly visits;

- oblige heads of enterprises to study the issue of their children being in preschool institutions or under the supervision of adults, upon the return of workers from maternity leave, and take measures to ensure the safety of children;

- recommend to the managers of enterprises that have a current work schedule, including at night, weekends and holidays, to install an API with signal output to alarm sound devices or to neighboring houses (apartments) for workers raising minor children.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that, taking into account the severity of this problem, district executive committees, labor and social protection departments of district executive committees, managers of various forms of ownership need to ensure funding and take measures to unconditionally implement the planned activities in full, in order to achieve a reduction in the number of fires and the deaths of people on them.

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